

Prevalence and Factors Associated with Self-Medication Among Pregnant Women Attending Antenatal Care at Lira Regional Referral Hospital

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Abstract: Background: Self-medication is defined as the use of manufactured or home-made drugs without medical prescriptions seeking to treat symptoms or self-diagnosed health conditions. It is universal challenge with an estimated 83.1% to 90% of pregnant women globally practicing it. SM can cause a serious harm to baby including developmental delays, fetal toxicities, intellectual disabilities, birth defects and miscarriage and harming the mother herself. SM practice during pregnancy has been increasing and found to be high in many regions of the world especially in developing countries. This objective therefore is to assess the prevalence and factors associated with self-medication among pregnant mothers at LRRH. Aims: To assess the prevalence and factors associated with SM among pregnant women at LRRH. Method: A descriptive cross-sectional study that used quantitative approach using a semi-structured interview questionnaire among 175 pregnant women was employed in determining the prevalence and factors associated with SM among pregnant women at Lira Regional Referral Hospital, the data was then entered, coded, cleaned and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Result: This study considered 175 participants where response rate was 100%. The prevalence of SM was found to be significantly high 87(49.7%) of the total participants. The leading indication for SM was body ache (34.1%) and malaria (33.3%) whereas analgesics (53.4%), anti-malaria (15.9%) drugs and cold and cough remedies (15.9%) were the classes of drug always self-medicated with. The major reasons given for SM were transport problem (30.3%), delayed patients service at facility/ (20.2%) and anticipated drug stockout at health facility (16.9%) meanwhile prior experience with the drug (AOR:51.84,95%CI:12.50-214.96, p:<0.001), and history of SM in previous pregnancy (AOR:10.04,95%CI:1.90-53.27, p:0.007) were the found to be the only factors associated with self-medication during pregnancy. Conclusion: In this study, self-medication is high among pregnant women at LRRH (49.7%), and the predictors for self-medication during pregnancy are prior experience with the drug and history of self-medication in previous pregnancy. More emphasis needs to be put on creation of awareness of the dangers of self-medication during pregnancy in order to reduce the vice.

Keywords: Self-medication, Associated factors, Prevalence

1. Introduction

Self-medication (SM) is defined as the use of manufactured or home-made drugs without medical prescriptions seeking to treat symptoms or self-diagnosed health conditions. In many developing

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countries where drugs are not well-regulated analgesics, anti-malarial, antibiotics, and cough syrups drugs are prone to self-medication of which analgesics are the most commonly used preparations (Zewdie et al., 2018). Self-medication is a universal challenge with an estimated 83.1% (Undela et al., 2020) to 90% of pregnant women globally practicing SM (Rahmani et al., 2019).

The practice is high among pregnant women across different continents with 34.8% pregnant women in Iran practicing SM and 77% of non-pregnant women practicing it (Botyar et al., 2018), 38.46% in Malaysia (Rahmani et al., 2019), 11.7% in Indonesia (Atmadani et al., 2020), 49% in United Arab Emirates (Mohamed Ibrahim et al., 2021), and 69% of pregnant women across European countries practicing SM (Trønnes et al., 2017). In the African continent, SM is a common practice among pregnant women with a prevalence of 16% in South Africa (Bulabula et al., 2020), 30.38% in Ethiopia (Adane, Seyoum, & Alamneh, 2020), 66.9% in Ghana (Gbagbo & Nkrumah, 2020), 72.4% in Democratic Republic of Congo (Abasiubong et al., 2018), 31.5 to 85% across Nigeria (Beyene & Beza, 2018). In East Africa and Tanzania in particular, the prevalence is 46.24% (Marwa et al., 2018) and in Uganda, particularly northern part, 75.7% of the general population practice SM with pregnant women being part of the population (Ocan et al., 2017).

Different population groups practice self-medication and pregnant women are among those exposed to SM practice (Jambo et al., 2018). SM is harmful to the health of all population groups with effects like drug toxicities, adverse drug reactions including hypersensitivity reactions. Pregnant women are however most affected due to altered drug pharmacokinetics and drugs crossing the placenta, possibly causing harm to the fetus (Jambo et al., 2018), resulting into developmental delays, fetal toxicities, intellectual disabilities, birth defects and miscarriage (Ahmed et al., 2020) and harming the mother herself.

Different strategies have been employed to curb the vice which involves educational approaches aimed at equipping people with knowledge on the dangers of self-medication to their health, mass sensitization and regulatory approaches aimed at controlling drug use and sales outlets.

There is however limited information on SM specifically with conventional medicine among pregnant women in Uganda as the few available literatures are concentrated in SM in the general population and on SM with herbal medicine for those among pregnant women. This study therefore aimed at evaluating the magnitude and the factors associated with SM specifically with conventional medicine among pregnant women at Lira regional referral hospital.

2. Methodology

Study design

The study employed a cross-sectional descriptive study design that used a quantitative approach to determine the prevalence and factors associated with self-medication among 175 pregnant women at Lira Regional Referral Hospital.

Study site

The study was carried out in Lira District located in Lango sub-region in Northern Uganda and is bordered by the districts of Pader and Otuke in the North and North East, Alebtong in the East, Dokolo in the South and Apac in the West. The district covers approximately a total area of 1326 km² of which 1286.22 km² is land area with a total population of 408,043 of which 196,663 are males and 211,380 are females (UBOS, 2017).

Study setting

The services offered at the health facility include surgery, gynecology and obstetrics care, medicine, dentistry and orthopedics, outpatient services such as immunization, HIV counseling and testing and elimination of mother to child transmission (eMTCT) and antenatal care services. The common diseases treated at the facility are malaria, tuberculosis, HIV/AIDS, pneumonia, abortion, anemia, hypertension and fractures due to road traffic accident.

Study population

This study targeted mainly pregnant women who were attending antenatal clinic at Lira Regional Referral Hospital.

Sampling size determination

The sample was determined us Cochran's formula (1977) as below;

$$N = \frac{Z^2 p q}{(ME)^2}$$

Where:

N = The sample size needed, Z= 1.96 deviation corresponding to 95% Confidence interval, P = 46.24% percentage prevalence of self-medication among pregnant women (Marwa et al., 2018), ME = Margin of Error (+/- 5%) and Q=1-p the remaining population which not under study and it corresponds to 53.76%

$$N = (1.96)^2 \times 0.4624 \times 0.5376$$

$$(0.05)^2 \quad N = 381 \quad \text{participants}$$

Using the finite population factor for sample size adjustment by Glenn D. Israel 1994

$$n = n_0 \times N / (n_0 + (N-1))$$

$$n = 381 \times 270 / (381 + (270 - 1)), n = 159.$$

Therefore, the sample size of the study is 175 participants considering 10 percent for non-responding participants

Sampling method

Consecutive sampling method was used to obtain the study sample. All pregnant women who met the inclusion criteria and consented were included in the study. This method is the method of choice because it is easy and suitable for a limited study population.

3. Data collection

Data collection method and tool

The data was collected using interview method. The interviews were conducted using semi-structured interview questionnaires.

Data collection procedure

Tool pretesting was done to ensure reliability and validity, an introductory and approval letter from Lira University Research ethics committee was presented to the District Health officer, Hospital director and the staffs of LRRH for further approval and a copy of approved letter was presented to the in charge antenatal unit, where permission to carry out the study was obtained.

After obtaining permission to conduct the study, consecutive sampling was done to select participants and afterwards, approach and self-introduction of eligible participants followed. The purpose of the study was explained to the participants and their consent obtained, then each participant was given an interviewer guided questionnaire containing systematically arranged questions which are constructed to yield close ended responses intended to meet all the specific objectives of the study. The individual questions were asked in English and then translated into the local language for those who could not understand English. Each interview session lasted for about 8 to 10 minutes.

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria: The study included all the pregnant women attending ANC clinic at Lira Regional Referral Hospital.

Exclusive criteria: Even after meeting the inclusive criteria the study excluded pregnant women who were mentally incapacitated. This is because they are unable to communicate effectively; hence the information they provide is more likely to be inaccurate and insufficient to meet the study objectives. It excluded all pregnant women who were severely ill, who could not be able to endure for the interview period.

Data management

Data entry and cleaning: After data collection, the questionnaires were checked for accuracy and completeness of the information collected. The data was then coded, entered and cleaned using SPSS version 23.0 to eliminate errors and inconsistencies that could occur during the entry process.

Data analysis and presentation: After data collection, analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. Univariate analysis was done using descriptive statistics to describe independent variables such as age, education level, marital status, occupation, parity, address which are presented as frequencies and percentages.

Bivariate analysis was done to find the association between dependent and independent variables using cross tabulation where categorical data (binary, ordinal or nominal data) were tested using Chi-Square (X^2) and simple binary logistic analysis for categorical variable. Multivariate logistic regression analysis was done to identify the associated factors of self-medication among pregnant women.

Quality control (validity & reliability)

To ensure that the instrument of the study is valid, relevant questions from other previous research studies were adapted into the questionnaire; the questionnaire was checked by experts including my supervisor, who assessed external and content validity. A pre-test study was carried out using consecutive sampling on a total of five participants from which responses were obtained for one day using the developed questionnaire as to enable modification of the tool to make it valid and reliable. Prior to data collection, the questionnaire was pretested among five mothers at Amuca SDA health center III to check for adequacy of questions in terms of wording, clarity and ambiguity before use in actual study setting.

Ethical considerations Approval

The approval to carry out the study was obtained from Lira University Research and Ethics Committee (LUREC), Lira District Health Officer and the Lira Regional Referral Hospital (LRRH) administrators including the in-charge of Antenatal clinic.

Consent

A document containing the purpose of the research, benefits of the research, the risks, and the rights of the participants was read to all respondents. They were asked to consent to the study after acknowledging that they understand and agree to participate in the study. They indicated consent by signing and or inserting a thumb print.

Privacy

Interviews took place in a private place where other people could not interrupt or hear what is being discussed and data was entered into SPSS and secured using a password.

Confidentiality

I used participants initials not their full names in order to shield their identity and information that were given by the participants and did not disclose to any other person. Only the research team was allowed to have access to the research data.

Study limitations

Non- response by the participants to certain questions in a questionnaire during data collection might affect the study by hindering data collection and it will be mitigated by establishing good rapport with the pregnant women. Recall bias as participant may not remember correctly their past self-medication use.

4. Results

Response rate

This study was conducted to assess the prevalence and factor associated with self-medication among pregnant women attending ANC at LRRH. In the study, 175 participants were considered and the response rate was 100%. The mothers were interviewed to capture their i) socio-demographic characteristics, ii) obstetric history, iii) medication use during pregnancy. This chapter presents the data obtained from questionnaire responses.

Sociodemographic characteristics

From the total, 175 participants interviewed 74(42%) were in the age between 15 to 24, 82(46%) between 25 to 34 years, and 19(10.9%) between 35 to 44 years of age. The marital status of the women was, 18(10.3%) single, majority that is 156(89.1%) married and 1(0.6%) of the women were divorced. Considering occupation, 63(36.0%) of the women were business women, 82(46.9%) were employed, 3(1.7%) were unemployed, 22(12.6%) were housewives, 5(2.9%) had other occupations. The level of education was, 5(2.9%) of women had no formal education, 25(14.3%) had incomplete primary school education, 44(25.1%) finished primary education, 72(41.1%) finished secondary education, and 29(16.6%) finished college or university education. From the 175 women, 146(83.4%) came from distance less than 5km from the nearest health facility and the rest, 29(16.6%) were from places more than 5km away from the health facility.

Table 1. Showing sociodemographic characteristics of participants.

Variable	Frequency(N)	Percentage (%)
Age		
15 -24	74	42.3
25-34	82	46.9
35-44	19	10.9
Total	175	100.0
Marital status		
Single	18	10.3
Married	156	89.1
Divorced	1	.6
Total	175	100.0
Occupation		
Business	63	36.0
Employed	82	46.9
Unemployed	3	1.7
Housewife	22	12.6
Others	5	2.9
Total	175	100.0
Highest level of education completed		
No Formal Education	5	2.9
Incomplete Primary School	25	14.3
Primary School	44	25.1
Secondary School	72	41.1
College Or University Level	29	16.6
Total	175	100.0
Distance from Health facility		
Less than 5 Km	146	83.4
More than 5Km	29	16.6
Total	175	100.0

Obstetric History

The gravidity of women out of 175 were, 43(24.6) gravida 1, 45(25.7%) gravida 2, 35(20.0%) gravida 3, 23(13.1%) gravida 4, 9(5.1%) gravida 5, 17(9.7%) gravida 6, 2(1.1%) gravida 7 and 1(0.6%) gravida 9. In this study, the parity of women out of 175 were, 53(30.3%) para 0, 44(25.1%) para 1, 37(21.1%) para 2, 21(12.0%) para 3, 8(4.6%) of the women were para 4, 10(5.7%) of the women were para 5, 1(0.6%) w a para 6, and 1(0.6%) was a para 8. The gestation age of the women was, 17(9.7%) of women between 4 to 12 weeks or first trimester, majority 116(66.3%) of women were between 13 to 28 weeks or second trimester and 42(24.0%) between 29 to 40 weeks of gestation or third trimester.

The distribution of obstetric complication among the 175 pregnant women were as follows, 48(90.6%) of the women had at least one miscarriage/abortion in their lives, 4(7.5%) of the pregnant women had at least 1 still birth in their lives, and 1(1.9%) of the pregnant women hand had other obstetric complications in their lives.

Figure 1. A bar chart showing Gravidity of women.

Figure 2. ; A bar chart showing the parity of the pregnant women at LRRH.

Figure 3. A pie chart showing Gestation Age of Pregnant women at LRRH.

Figure 4. A pie chart showing obstetric complication history among pregnant women at LRRH.

Medication Uses during Pregnancy

The result on medication use during pregnancy shows that majority, 140(80%) of the pregnant women used medication during pregnancy and 35(20.0%) of the pregnant women did not use any medication in their current pregnancy. When asked how they obtained the medicines/drugs, 53(30.3%) of the pregnant women reported obtained through doctors' prescription, 87(49.7%) of the pregnant women obtained through self-order from pharmacy/drug shop/clinic and 35(20.0%) constituted those who did not use any medicine. Of the 175 pregnant women at LRRH, 87(49.7%) practiced self-medication in their current pregnancy.

Of those who used any medication during pregnancy, 96(54.9%) had use the drug before in life, and 79(45.1%) had not. Out of 175 pregnant women, 58(33.1%) used non prescribed drug in the previous pregnancy, and majority 117(66.9%) did not use non prescribed drug in the previous pregnancy. From the total study participants, 121(69.1%) had sickness/illness during their current pregnancy and minority 54(30.9%) did not have not have any sickness. In addition, 16 (9.1%) of the pregnant women had history of chronic illness. The result also shows that 46(34.1%) of the women who used medication during pregnancy used to treat body ache, 44(33.3%) to treat malaria, 13(9.6%) to treat flue, 15(11.1%) to treat cough, 1(0.7%) to treat vomiting, 15(11.1%) to treat other health problems.

The classes of drugs always self-medicated are; anti-malarial 14(15.9%) of those practice self-medication, 9(10.2%) of pregnant women practice self-medication with antibiotic, 1(1.1%) with antiemetic, majority of women 47(53.4%) with analgesics, 3(3.4%) with antiasthma and 14(15.9%) of the pregnant women practiced self-medication with cough and cold remedies. The reasons given for self-medication among those who practice self-medication were; transport problem by 27(30.3%) of women, anticipated drug stock out at health facility 15(16.9%) of women, severe illness 9(10.1%) of women, late onset of illness during the course of the day 9(10.1%) of women, delayed patients

service at health facility 18(20.2%) of women, emergency situations 7(7.9%) of women, and hostile health professional at health facility 4(4.5%) of the women.

Table 2. showing results on medication use among pregnant women.

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Frequency(N)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
<i>Used Medication in this Pregnancy.</i>		
<i>Yes</i>	140	80.0
<i>No</i>	35	20.0
<i>Total</i>	175	100.0
<i>How the drug/medicine was obtained</i>		
<i>Prescribed by doctor</i>	53	30.3
<i>Self-ordered from pharmacy/drug shop/clinic</i>	87	49.7
<i>None</i>	35	20.0
<i>Total</i>	175	100.0
<i>Self-medication practice.</i>		
<i>Yes</i>	87	49.7
<i>No</i>	88	50.3
<i>Total</i>	175	100.0
<i>Used the drug before in life.</i>		
<i>Yes</i>	96	54.9
<i>No</i>	79	45.1
<i>Total</i>	175	100.0
<i>Used nonprescribed drug in previous pregnancy</i>		
<i>Yes</i>	58	33.1
<i>No</i>	117	66.9
<i>Total</i>	175	100.0
<i>Had illness/sickness after confirming current pregnancy.</i>		
<i>Yes</i>	121	69.1
<i>No</i>	54	30.9
<i>Total</i>	175	100.0
<i>Mother or her child had chronic illness</i>		
<i>Yes</i>	16	9.1
<i>No</i>	159	90.9
<i>Total</i>	175	100.0

Figure 5. showing prevalence of self-medication among pregnant women attending ANC clinic at LRRH.

Figure 6. Showing Health problem the medications are used to treat.

Figure 7. Showing the kinds/classes of drugs always self-medicated by pregnant women at LRRH.

Figure 8. Showing the reasons why pregnant women at LRRH opt to go for self-medication.

Factors associated with self-medication among pregnant women attending ANC at LRRH:

To find out the factors associated with self-medication among pregnant women at LRRH, bivariate analysis was done where the independent variables was cross tabulated with the dependent variable(self-medication) using chi-square to determine the association between each independent variable and self-medication practice. In addition, simple binary logistic regression analysis was done to determine association between independent variables with more than two categories and the dependent variable. The study result shows that out of 16 independent variables, four that is having used the drug before (COR:177.3395%CI:48.20-652.41, $p < 0.001$), using nonprescribed drug in the previous pregnancy (COR:77.68,95%CI:17.88-337.50, $p < 0.001$), having had sickness in the current pregnancy (COR:10.82,95%CI:4.67-25.02, $p < 0.001$), and maternal age categories 15-24($p:0.037$) and 25-34($p:0.046$) were associated with self-medication among pregnant women.

The odds of self-medication were 177.3 for those who used the drug before, 77.7 for those who used non prescribed drugs in the previous pregnancy and 10.8 for those who had sickness in their current pregnancy. To find out the factors that were significantly associated with self-medication among pregnant women at LRRH, multivariate analysis was done where the factors that were associated with SM in the bivariate analysis were subjected to a binary logistic regression. The result shows that prior experience with drug (used drug before in life) and previous history of self-medication (previous pregnancy non prescribed drug use) were the only factors significantly associated with self-medication during pregnancy with p -values of < 0.001 and 0.007 respectively.

Table 3. Showing bivariate analysis of each independent variable and dependent variable using chi-square and simple binary logistic regression analysis.

Variable	Self-medication		p-value	B	X ²	COR:95%CI.
	Yes	No				
Age						
15-24	34(39.1%)	40(45.5%)	0.037	-1.192	4.939	0.304(0.099-0.929)
25-34	39(44.8%)	43(48.9%)	0.046	-1.127		0.324(0.107-0.982)

34-44)	14(16.1%)	5(5.7%)	Reference	1		1
Marital status						
Single	7(8.0%)	40(45.5%)	1.000	- 21.655		0.000
Married)	79(90.8%)	43(48.9%)	1.000	- 21.177	1.909	0.000
Divorced	1(1.1%)	5(5.7%)	Reference	1	1	1
Occupation						
Business)	22(25.3%)	26(29.5%)	0.448	- 0.288		0.749(0.356-1.550)
Employed)	30(34.5%)	31(35.2%)	0.665	- 0.154	6.399	0.857(0.427-1.79)
Unemployed)	35(40.2%)	31(35.2%)	Reference	1	1	1
Highest level of education						
No formal education	2(2.35)	3(3.4%)	0.733	- 0.336		0.741(0.103-4.930)
Incomplete primary education)	13(14.9%)	12(13.6%)	0.785	0.14 9		1.161(0.398-3.386)
Primary education)	23(26.4%)	21(23.9%)	0.738	0.16 0	0.981	1.173(0.459-2.999)
Secondary education)	35(40.2%)	37(42.0%)	0.976	0.01 3		1.014(0.428-22.401)
College or Tertiary education)	14(16.1%)	15(17.0%)	Reference	1	1	1
Distance from facility						
<5km)	68(78.2%)	78(88.6%)	0.066	- 0.779	3.472	0.459(0.200-1.554)
>5k)	19(21.85%)	10(11.4%)	Reference	1	1	1
Gravidity						
1)	23(26.4%)	20(22.7%)	1.000	- 21.063		0.000
2)	17(19.5%)	28(31.8%)	1.000	- 21.707		0.000
3)	17(19.5%)	18(20.5%)	1.000	- 21.260		0.000
4)	15(17.2%)	8(9.1%)	1.000	- 20.574	9.111	0.000
5)	3(3.4%)	6(6.8%)	1.000	- 21.896		0.000
6)	9(10.3%)	8(9.1%)	1.000	- 21.085		0.000
7)	2(2.3%)	0(0.0%)	1.000	0.00 0		0.000
9)	1(1.1%)	0(0.0%)	Reference	1		1
Parity						
0)	23(26.4%)	30(34.1%)	1.000	- 21.469		0.000

1	21(24.1%)	23(26.1%)	1.000	- 21.294		0.000
2	21(24.15%)	16(18.2%)	1.000	- 20.931	9.333	0.000
3	10(11.5%)	11(12.5%)	1.000	- 21.298		0.000
4	2(2.35%)	6(6.5%)	1.000	- 21.302		0.000
5	8(9.2%)	2(2.3%)	1.000	- 19.817		0.000
6	1(1.1%)	0(0.0%)	1.000	0.00 0		0.000
8	1(1.1%)	0(0.0%)	Referen ce	1		1
Gestation age						
4-12	5(5.7%)	12(13.6%)	0.131	- 0.684		0.504(0.151- 1.6870)
13-28	68(72.4%)	53(60.25%)	0.267	0.36 2	4.120	1.439(0.708- 2.924)
29-40	19(21.8%)	23(26.1%)	Referen ce	1		1
Miscarriage						
Yes	19(21.8%)	29(33.4%)	0.101	- 0.565	2,716	0.568(0.289- 1.117)
No	68(78.2%)	59(67%)	Referen ce	1		1
History of still birth						
Yes	2(2.3%)	2(2.3%)	0.991	0.01 2	0.000	1.012(0.139- 7.348)
No	85(97.7%)	86(97.7%)	Referen ce	1	1	1
Intrauterine fetal death						
Yes	-	-	-	-	-	-
No	87(100%)	88(100%)	1	1	1	1
Other obstetric complication.						
Yes	0(0.0%)	1(1.1%)	1.000	- 21.203	0.999	0.000
No	87(100%)	87(98.8%)	Referen ce	1	1	1
Used the drug before						
Yes	56(64.4%)	2(2.3%)	0.000	5.17 8	121.45 4	177.333(48.20 1-652.412)
No	31(35.6%)	86(97.7%)	1	1		1
Previous pregnancy nonprescribed drug use.						
Yes	56(64.4%)	2(2.3%)	0.000	4.35 3	76.127	77.677(17.878 -337.49)
No	31(35.6%)	86(97.7%)	1	1	1	1
Current pregnancy illness.						
Yes	79(90.8%)	42(47.7%)	0.000	2.38 1	38.050	10.815(4.674- 25.025)

No	8(9.2%)	46(52.3%)	Reference	1	1	1
Chronic illness.						
Yes	10(11.5%)	6(6.8%)	0.288	0.574	1.152	1.177(0.616-5.117)
No	77(88.5%)	82(93.2%)	Reference	1	1	1

Table 4. Showing results for multivariate logistic regression analysis to determine the predictors of self-medication during pregnancy.

Variable	B-coefficient	P-value	AOR	95% CI for AOR	
				Lower	Upper
Age					
15-24	-0.050	0.966	0.951	0.093	9.749
25-34	-0.104	0.292	0.901	0.092	8.818
Used the drug before in life.	3.948	0.000	51.836	12.500	214.956
Previous pregnancy nonprescribed drug use	2.307	0.007	10.042	1.893	53.274
Current pregnancy illness.	0.874	0.263	2.397	0.519	11.080

5. Discussion of Results

Prevalence of self-medication

The practice of SM is a global challenge that requires high attention because it poses a potential threat to the pregnant mother and fetus. The actual magnitude of SM and its contributing factors in developing countries like Uganda may not be known to health professional who provide medical help to these women during pregnancy. Conducting a study like this will therefore help them to design and develop strategies to prevent/minimize SM practice during pregnancy. This study, therefore, investigated the practice of SM with conventional (modern) medicines and its contributing factors among pregnant women attending ANC clinic at LRRH. The study revealed that a great proportion of pregnant women practiced SM without consulting healthcare professional.

Though harmful to the mother and her unborn baby, nearly half, 49.7% of pregnant women at LRRH practice SM. The prevalence is comparable with that in united Arab emirate (Mohamed Ibrahim et al., 2021), Tanzania (Marwa et al., 2018), and that reported in northern Ethiopia (Sema et al., 2020). It is more than three times the prevalence reported from Indonesia (Atmadani et al., 2020), that from south Africa (Bulabula et al., 2020), and it is nearly one-half the result reported in Tehran Iran (Botyar et al., 2018), national in Ethiopia (Adane et al., 2020) and that conducted in Saudi Arabia (Raheel et al., n.d.) and nationally in Iran (Rahmani et al., 2019).

It is nearly 20% less than that from a study conducted in Ghana (Gbagbo & Nkrumah, 2020) and that from Harar town Ethiopia (Jambo et al., 2018). It is about 30% less than result of study done in Malaysia which is 81.4% (Alani et al., 2020). These variations could be attributed to the differences in level of health education during antenatal visits on the risks of self-medication in pregnancy, population demographics, access to healthcare service, and restriction policies of dispensing practices. It is lower when compared with the prevalence of self-medication reported in the general population in 2017 in northern Uganda (Ocan et al., 2017).

Accordingly, 44(33.3%) and 46(34.1%) were the leading indications for self-medication which is similar to that done in Tigray Ethiopia where morning sickness, headache and upper respiratory tract infection were the leading indication for self-medication during pregnancy (Niriayo et al., 2021) and study done in north west Ethiopia where headache was the major indication for self-medication during pregnancy (Sema et al., 2020). Meanwhile the leading classes of drug self-medicated with are analgesics 47(53.4%), anti-malarial 14(15.9%), and cough and cold remedies 14(15.9%). In a study done in Ethiopia, the major drug self-medicated with was paracetamol (analgesic) (Sema et al., 2020).

The major reason for self-medication were transport problem 27(30.3%), delayed patients service at health facility 18(20.2%) and anticipated drug stock out at health facility 15(16.9%) whereas in a study done in Ethiopia, ease of access to drug, feeling that the disease is minor and prolonged waiting time were the reasons given for self-medication (Niriayo et al., 2021).

Factors associated with self-medication during pregnancy

From the 16 independent variables considered in the bivariate analysis, four factors that is prior experience with the drug (COR:177.3395%CI:48.20-652.41, $p<0.001$), history of self-medication in previous pregnancy (COR:77.68,95%CI:17.88-337.50, $p<0.001$), maternal illness in current pregnancy (COR:10.82,95%CI:4.67-25.02, $p<0.001$), and maternal age categories 15-24($p:0.037$) and 25-34($p:0.046$) were found to be associated with self-medication among pregnant women. When the factors were subjected to binary logistic regression however, prior experience with the drug/having used the drug before in life (AOR:51.84,95%CI:12.50-214.96, $p<0.001$), and history of self-medication in the previous pregnancy used/nonprescribed drug in previous pregnancy (AOR:10.04,95%CI:1.90-53.27, $p:0.007$) were found to be significantly associated with self-medication during pregnancy.

The finding is consistent with that done in Ethiopia (Adane, Seyoum, & Alamneh, 2020) , northwestern Ethiopia (Sema et al., 2020), and that conducted among pregnant women in Addis Ababa Ethiopia (Beyene & Beza, 2018) where previous history of self-medication was a predictor for self-medication during pregnancy. The possible explanation could be because they did not find any pregnancy complication when they used the respective drugs in the previous pregnancy and hence feel it is safe to self-medicate during pregnancy. In addition, the result of the study finding is in accordance with that done in north Eastern Ethiopia where prior experience with the drug was associated with self-medication during pregnancy (Tuha et al., 2020). This could be attributed to the fact that they know some information about drug indication and dosage hence can just make order for it from a drug shop, clinic or pharmacy.

There was however no association found between age and self-medication among pregnant women at LRRH. This is in contrast with studies done in Ethiopia (Sema et al., 2020), (Beyene & Beza, 2018) and that reported from Tanzania (Marwa et al., 2018). On the other hand, employment status was not associated with SM during pregnancy as in study reported from Ethiopia (Beyene & Beza, 2018) meanwhile gestation age and education level were found not to be associated with SM as reported in Tanzania (Marwa et al., 2018) and southern Ethiopia (Zewdie et al., 2018). The difference could be attributed to the difference in study population's demographic characteristics.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, self-medication is high among pregnant women at LRRH (49.7%), and the predictors for self-medication during pregnancy are prior experience with the drug and history of self-medication in previous pregnancy. More emphasis needs to be put on creation of awareness of the dangers of self-medication during pregnancy in order to reduce the vice and ensure the health of pregnant women and most importantly their unborn fetus. Also, regulation policies on drug use in the country have to be reinforced by national drug authority to make sure that women are protected at drug dispensing points. More studies need to be done in different facilities within district, northern region and Uganda at large to give a real picture of the problem.

Abbreviation;

HIV/AIDS: Human Immunodeficiency virus /Acquired Immunodeficiency Virus.

LUREC: Lira University Research Ethic Committee.

OTCDs: Over the Counter Drugs.

UBOS: Uganda Bureau of statistics.

WHO: World Health Organization.

Declaration of conflict of interest:

The authors declared no conflict of interest concerning the study.

Ethical considerations:

The approval to carry out the study will be obtained from Lira University Research and Ethics Committee (LUREC) and the Lira Regional Referral Hospital (LRRH) administrators including the in-charge of Antenatal clinic.

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